

Structure of a Nonionic Water-soluble Galactomannan from the Seeds of *Ipomea reptan*

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The plants of genera *Ipomea*¹ have been reported for their therapeutic value and are also a good source of mucilages. Stems of *Ipomea fistulosa*² is used for the production of biogas. The medicinal values and wide industrial use have prompted us to undertake a structural study of the polysaccharide isolated from the seeds of *Ipomea reptan*.

Results and Discussion

A galactomannan obtained from the defatted and decolourised seeds with 1% aqueous acetic acid, was purified by (i) repeated precipitation from a large excess of ethanol (90%), (ii) via copper complex formation and (iii) deproteinisation. Its homogeneity was tested by fractional precipitation, zone electrophoresis and p.c in different solvent systems.

The polysaccharide (P.S.), $[\alpha]_D^{30} +40^\circ$ (water), was soluble in water and had an ash content of 0.3%. Methoxyl, acetyl, carboxyl and uronide contents were negligible, while N, S, P and halogens were absent. Complete hydrolysis with 1M sulphuric acid and quantification indicated the presence of D-galactose and D-mannose in the molar ratio of 1 : 3. On graded hydrolysis with 0.25 M sulphuric acid, D-galactose was released earlier than D-mannose, indicating D-galactose as terminal group linked probably by α -bonds and mannose constituting the main-chain. Methylation of the P.S. by Haworth's method yielded a partly methylated P.S. which on further methylation by Purdie's method resulted in completely methylated polysaccharide, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 38^\circ$ (chloroform). Hydrolysis of methylated P.S. afforded 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose, 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 2.

The formation of the above three methylated sugars indicated that in the case of 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose, position O-1, in case of 2,3,6-trio-O-methyl-D-mannose, positions O-1, O-4 and in case of 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose, positions O-1, O-4, O-6 are engaged in glycosidic linkage. The involvement of position O-1 of the galactose units in glycosidic linkage fixes its place as non-reducing terminal groups and the attachment through O-1, O-4, O-6 positions of the mannose units suggests their place at the branching points or as a prime constituent of the main-chain. Further attachment through O-1, O-4 of mannose units by the side of the branching point and constitute main-chain, i.e. mannose units are backbone of the P.S. The polysaccharide showed IR bands at 810 and 875 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of both α and β linkages.

On the basis of these results the repeating unit of the P.S. consists of four sugar moieties of which one galactose unit occupies as non-reducing terminal group and three mannose units form the main-chain. Periodate oxidation studies showed the liberation of 154 mM of formic acid with the consumption of 771 mM of oxidant per 100 g of the polysaccharide, which indicated 27.62% end-group supported by methylation studies 28% per repeating of the P.S. Examination of the oxidation products after 72 h showed complete absence of galactose whereas mannose was absent after 96 h. Partial acid hydrolysis of the P.S. resulted epimelibiose, galactosylmannobiose, mannobiose and mannotriose.

Considering all the above results the most tenable structural pattern of the repeating units of the polysaccharide has been elucidated as

Experimental

All the concentrations were carried out at diminished pressure and low temperature. M.ps. are uncorrected and all optical rotations are equilibrium values. Identities of the compounds were confirmed by m.m.p. and paper chromatography using the following solvent mixtures (v/v) : (A) 1-butanol-ethanol-water, 5 : 1 : 4³, (B) 1-butanol-2-propanol-water, 11 : 6 : 3⁴, (C) ethyl acetate-pyridine-water, 10 : 4 : 3⁵, (D), ethyl acetate-pyridine-water, 2 : 1 : 2⁶, (E) 1-butanol-ethanol-water, 31 : 11 : 9⁷. Emulsion for enzymatic hydrolysis was extracted from almonds. Sugar spots in p.c. were located with the help of aniline hydrogen phthalate. All residues were dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The crushed and dried seeds of *I. reptan* were treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and ethanol respectively to remove fat and colouring matters, and then suspended in 1% acetic acid for 24 h. Polysaccharide was precipitated by 95% ethanol and dried over fused calcium chloride. It was purified by deproteinisation with chloroform⁸ and complexation with Fehling's solution⁹ : $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 44^\circ$ (water), ash content 0.3%. Homogeneity was checked by fractional precipitation, zone electrophoresis¹⁰, and acetylation¹¹ and deacetylation methods.

Complete hydrolysis of the P.S. (1 g) by 1 M sulphuric acid for 30 h at 100° yielded D-galactose and D-mannose, which were separated by p.c. using solvent (B), and which on quantification (sodium metaperiodate)¹² gave a molar ratio of 1 : 3. These were identified by co-chromatography with authentic samples, m.p. and preparation of their derivatives : D-galactose, m.p. 164°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 80^\circ$ (water) : D-galactose phenylhydrazone, m.p. 153°; D-mannose, m.p. 131°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 14^\circ$ (water); D-mannose phenylhydrazone, m.p. 196°. Graded hydrolysis of the P.S. (300 mg) with 25 mM sulphuric acid indicated the early release of D-galactose followed by D-mannose. Periodate oxidation of the P.S. (300 mg) with 0.25 M sodium metaperiodate solution¹⁴ showed the presence of 154 mM formic acid per 100 g of the P.S. After 72 h, an excess of ethylene glycol was added to it, the mixture evaporated to dryness and the residue on hydrolysis revealed the complete absence of galactose and mannose.

The P.S. (8 g) was completely^{15,16} and the complete methylation was confirmed by the absence of ir band at 3 200–3 600 cm^{-1} . The methylated product (2 g) was hydrolysed with 90% formic acid (6 h, 100°) and then with 0.75 M sulphuric acid (10 h, 100°). The hydrolysate was separated by P.C. (solvent A) using 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose (TMG) as reference sugar. The following methylated sugars were isolated and quantified by hypobromite method in the ratio of 1 : 1 : 2 : 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose, R_{TMG} 0.87, $[\alpha]_D^{32} + 120.3^\circ$ (water), m.p. 73° (lit.¹⁷ + 121°, 74°), the anilide $[\alpha]_D^{32} + 44^\circ$ (acetone), m.p. 193° (lit.¹⁷ + 45°, 194°); 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose, R_{TMG} 0.53, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 16^\circ$ (water), m.p. 107–08° (lit.¹⁸, -15.8°, 108°); the anilide, m.p. 137° (lit. 138°), 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose : R_{TMG} 0.80 syrup, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 11^\circ$ (lit.^{19,20} -10° (water)); the hydrazide, m.p. 130°.

Partial acid hydrolysis of the P.S. (4.5 g) with 0.05 M sulphuric acid for 14 h at 100° and the separation of the products by p.c. (solvent D) gave D-galactose, D-mannose along with the following oligosaccharides : (i) epimelibiose, 6-O- α -D-galactosyl-D-mannose²¹, m.p. 200° $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 122^\circ$ (water) (lit.¹⁹ 201°–02° 121–24°). Acid hydrolysis gave galactose and mannose in equimolar proportion. Methylation and subsequent hydrolysis gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose. It was not hydrolysed by emulsion, (ii) galactosyl mannobiose, 6-O- α -D-galactosyl(1 \rightarrow 6) β -D-mannosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)-D-mannose²¹, m.p. 227°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 92-93^\circ$ (water). Partial acid hydrolysis and subsequent p.c. (solvent D) gave mannobiose, epimelibiose, galactose and mannose. During periodate oxidation 6.02 mol was consumed and 2.98 moles of formic acid was liberated, (iii) mannobiose^{22,23}, 4-

O- β -D-mannosyl-D-mannose, m.p. 204°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 10.1^\circ$ (water) (lit.²⁰ 202–03°, -5.2 to -8.2°). Its phenylhydrazone had m.p. 203° (lit. 203–06°). Acid hydrolysis gave D-mannose only. Methylation and subsequent hydrolysis yielded 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-mannose and 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose. It was cleaved by emulsion showing the presence of β -linkage and (iv) mannotriose^{22,23}, 4-O- β -D-mannosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- β -D-mannosyl-D-mannose, m.p. 211–13°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 14^\circ$ (water) (lit.²² 214–15°, -15° to -26°). Acid hydrolysis indicated the presence of D-mannose only, whereas partial acid hydrolysis afforded mannose and mannobiose. It was hydrolysed by emulsion showing the presence of β -linkage. Methylation and subsequent hydrolysis gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-mannose and 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose.

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